

AI-related R&D and socio-economic divide in Canada: Gender, age and intersectional analysis

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Abstract

This research intends to address to what extent artificial intelligence (AI) can exacerbate or alleviate the divide between different socio-economic groups in terms of employment and wage. With the use of bibliometric analysis, this study intends to provide a better understanding of how the development of AI-related technologies is associated with the employment of women and the ageing population. For this purpose, the study analyzes the industries in which Canadian companies involved in AI-related research and development (R&D) operate. It further identifies how these industries are inclusive for women, older adults and the ageing population and the intersection of the two. The results show that the gender gap in the employment and wage rate is evident in AI-associated industries and that these gender gaps are the highest among the ageing population.

Introduction

The field of artificial intelligence (AI) is broadly described as intelligence exhibited by machines to perform specific tasks. AI is based on the idea of simulating natural intelligence displayed by humans. It is utilized in an ample number of industries through its seven core avenues: machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, cognitive computing, expert systems, speech recognition, and robotics. Therefore, the applications of AI range from simple tasks, such as developing a chatbot to answer basic questions, to complex work, like identifying cancerous cells in mammogram images. In essence, AI revolutionizes a vast variety of industries by incorporating machinery to imitate human capabilities of performing repetitive tasks for long durations.

Based on its many capabilities, AI is destined to affect economic growth by increasing productivity and efficiency in organizations through automating manually-performed tasks. As well it offers the opportunity to create new products, services, markets, and industries, which can influence consumer demand and generate new revenue streams (Szczepanski, 2019). On the contrary, there are conflicting perspectives on the effects of employment and society as AI becomes more incorporated into the industrial environment. For instance, the development of AI can require the demand for higher technical skills in employment and consumers, which can increase inequality for older age groups (Szczepanski, 2019).

The growing hype around AI and its potential industrial benefits has also burgeoned a significant focus of government spending worldwide—especially Canada is attempting to become a leader in AI. In accordance, Canada appointed the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research to develop and lead a \$125 million Pan-Canadian Artificial Intelligence Strategy, being the world’s first national AI strategy. Since the program’s initiation in 2017, it has produced a 3.6% growth in tech employment, \$658 million in venture capital funding to Canadian AI start-ups, and over 45 new AI R&D labs established by major multinational firms (CIFAR, 2020). As well, \$1 billion in government contributions have been awarded across Canada as of August 2020, with an additional \$1.2 billion of planned government investments for the province of Quebec (Brandusescu, 2021). Potential reasons behind Canada’s high investment in AI are that the country strives to remain a top leading innovator in research and development (R&D) while also supporting a competitive environment for growing organizations. For instance, Canada is acknowledged as a world-leading AI research hub as they are within the top five countries to contribute towards the production of innovative AI research (Quiroz and Elahi, 2020). Moreover, between 2015 and 2018, Canada filed the highest number of AI patents per capita amongst the G7 and China (University of Toronto, 2020). This is a strong indication of their influence on global AI innovation, as patents are the main intermediary for measuring a nation’s innovation in certain fields. Lastly, Canada lists as the 4th out of a study of 54 countries in the Global AI Index based on its global competitiveness in AI implementation, innovation, and investment (Quiroz and Elahi, 2020).

Despite these initiatives inducing a vast industrial impact in Canada, there is a lack of consideration towards the socio-economic divide of the affiliated citizens. As such, the concept of “responsible AI” was conceived for companies to design and construct AI systems that do not intentionally impose negative impacts on employment or its consumers (Szczepanski, 2019). However, the ethical and societal concerns around AI mostly consider inequity from the viewpoint of the distribution of benefits from the use of AI and it rarely addresses inequity concerns related to the capacity of a diversified and inclusive workforce for AI development and commercialization. Along these lines, the concerns over “responsible AI” also revolve around the former rather than the latter aspect, accounting for diversity (of gender, age, identity groups, etc.) in algorithms, datasets, and other learning mechanisms. Therefore, this study intends to fill this gap and explores the relationship between AI and the Canadian workforce in terms of employment and wage and provides a better understanding of how the development of AI-related technologies is associated with the employment of equity-seeking groups. For this purpose, the study first analyzes the industries in which Canadian companies involved in AI-related R&D operate. It further identifies how these industries are inclusive for women, older adults and the ageing population and the intersections of these groups of people.

This study applies the techno-economic (TEN) framework (Bell and Callon, 1994) to analyze AI’s systems of innovation in Canada. TEN framework is an actor-network approach applicable to all types of innovation—either failed or successful, radical or incremental—and is organized around three major poles, science, technology and market and one minor pole, finance. Science, technology and market poles are considered the major ones because they are directly involved in the innovation process, while the finance pole mainly plays a supporting role. These poles are characterized by the “intermediaries” that they put into circulation to link the actors. These intermediaries include but are not limited to explicit knowledge or disembodied information, embodied knowledge or technical artifacts, tacit knowledge or skills and expertise, and money. Publications, patents, and socio-economic information are the main intermediaries to define major poles—science, technology and market pole, respectively (Islam and Miyazaki, 2009).

Methods

This study utilizes the TEN framework to better understand the socio-economic dimensions of AI, analyzing relevant publication, patent, company, and socio-economic data. We first use patent assignee and author affiliation data to identify Canadian companies involved in developing AI-related R&D.

AI-related patents are extracted from the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) database, using the US Class 706 (Data Processing - Artificial Intelligence) and its concordance to IPC8 subclasses¹. The data is refined to AI-related patents granted to Canadian companies or corporations between the years 2000-2020 using filter keywords for institutional sectors introduced in Ghiasi et al. (2015). Overall, 1437 AI-related patents were identified, among which 1412 were assigned to companies.

We further analyzed the Canadian companies involved in contributing towards AI-related R&D by the use of author affiliation data retrieved from AI-related papers from the Inspec database, one of the largest engineering research databases. Compared to other databases, an advantage of this database is that each paper indexed in Inspec is assigned to multiple subject classification codes (similar to World Intellectual Property Organization's (WPO) IPC codes)—alphanumeric codes assigned to the hierarchy of technical disciplines. It is important to note that Inspec also indexes open-access repositories of e-prints, such as ArXiv, which are essential to the field of artificial intelligence. After identifying the Subject Classification Codes related to AI, we extracted those papers authored by at least one Canadian author from the industry in the years 2000-2020. Overall, 29,896 AI-related papers were identified with at least one author affiliated to a Canadian institution, among which 1135 were affiliated to a Canadian corporation.

To determine the primary industries where these companies are located, we associated them with their primary North American Industry Classification System (NAICS) code using the Mergent intellect and Mergent online company information databases. We further validated the affiliated company's information by referencing business information to match the company's headquarters, current or prior locations, active years, and type of service. These industries were further assigned to Statistics Canada (StatCan)'s Labour Force Survey's (LFS) table 14-10-0064-01 (Employee wages by industry, annual (x 1,000)) (Statistics Canada 2022).

As an outcome, we associated the NAICS code with the assigned Canadian companies on 1278 (out of 1412) patents. As well, we identified the NAICS code to 904 (out of 1135) publications with at least one affiliated Canadian company. Employment data are further assigned at the year of publication or granting to capture the socio-economic dimensions and ensure that the company was active at the time.

The employment data are defined by both the number of patents and papers and the primary industry of the companies involved in AI-related R&D efforts. The employment rate is identified by dividing the number of persons employed in each group by the total number of persons employed. We further calculated the gender gap in employment and wage as the difference between men and women employed to that of men. We also used the average employment rate and median hourly wage at the level of all industries from 2000 to 2020 as a baseline for comparison.

¹Available at: <https://www.uspto.gov/web/patents/classification/uspc706/us706toipc8.htm>

Results

Our results reveal that the gender gap in employment is substantially higher in AI-related industries than in all Canadian industries (37% compared to 3%) (Table 1). The median hourly wage rate in AI-associated industries is 20.01 CAD for women and 25.47 CAD for men for both full- and part-time employees (Table 2). Although the median wage rate is higher in AI-related industries, the gender gap in the hourly wage rate is higher compared to that of all Canadian industries (21% compared to 16%). Women form the majority of part-time employees who are paid the lowest. However, even among part-time employees, men are paid 1% more in AI-related industries (Table 2). Figure 1 also reveals that the gender gap in the hourly wage rate is decreasing over time. However, when it comes to the gender gap in the employment rate, no such trend can be found.

Table 1. Number of employees (x1000) by employment type and gender

Number of employees (x1000)	Both full- and part-time employees		Full-time employees		Part-time employees	
	AI-related	ALL	AI-related	ALL	AI-related	ALL
Females	481.25	1115.36	398.96	837.34	82.76	291.34
Males	769.24	1147.78	721.01	1020.75	48.59	136.49
Gender gap	37%	3%	45%	18%	-70%	-113%

Table 2. Median hourly wage rate by employment type and gender

Median hourly wage rate	Both full- and part-time employees		Full-time employees		Part-time employees	
	AI-related	ALL	AI-related	ALL	AI-related	ALL
Females	20.01	18.62	21.00	19.63	15.35	14.88
Males	25.47	22.26	26.33	23.51	15.58	14.44
Gender gap	21%	16%	20%	16%	1%	-3%

Figure 1. Employment (top) and median hourly wage (bottom) rate by gender in Canada (left); Gender gap in employment (top) and wage (bottom) rate in AI-associated industries and all industries (right)

Overall, regarding the composition of employees by age, AI-associated industries are formed similarly to that of all Canadian industries. Younger adults (15 to 24 years) hold the highest share of part-time employees and are subject to lower hourly wage rate in AI-related industries (Tables 3 and 4). The employment rate of the ageing population has increased over time in both AI-related and all industries (Figure 2).

Table 3. Employment rate by employment type and gender

Employment rate	Both full- and part-time employees		Full-time employees		Part-time employees	
	AI-related	ALL	AI-related	ALL	AI-related	ALL
15 to 24 years	13%	17%	9%	11%	44%	44%
25 to 54 years	71%	69%	75%	75%	37%	40%
55 years and over	16%	15%	16%	14%	19%	16%

Table 4. Median hourly wage rate by employment type and age

Median hourly wage rate	Both full- and part-time employees		Full-time employees		Part-time employees	
	AI-related	ALL	AI-related	ALL	AI-related	ALL
15 to 24 years	15.27	13.75	16.14	14.79	12.41	11.40
25 to 54 years	24.69	22.30	25.12	22.90	17.37	16.74
55 years and over	24.47	21.43	25.59	22.60	18.56	16.44

Figure 2. Employment (top) and median hourly wage (bottom) rate by age in Canada in AI-associated industries and all industries

Interestingly, when it comes to intersectional analysis and when gender is also factored in, the gender gap in the employment and hourly wage rate is most evident among the ageing population. Even among part-time employees, where women are more present among the ageing population, men are paid substantially higher (Figure 3). Moreover, the gender gap in the hourly wage rate is the highest for full-time employees of 55 years old and over, among whom the gender gap in employment is also the highest.

Figure 3. Gender gap in employment (top) and wage (bottom) rate by age in AI-associated industries and all industries

Discussions

This study provides a better understanding of how the development of AI-related technologies is associated with the rate and type of employment of women, the ageing population, and the intersection of the two. The results showed that the gender gap in the employment and wage rate is more evident in AI-associated industries compared to those of all Canadian industries. Moreover, this study sheds light on the importance of intersectional analysis and shows that these gender gaps are the highest among women of the ageing population.

The lack of representation of women (especially women of the ageing population) in the development of AI might not only have consequences for the social inclusion of the Canadian workforce but also could impact the inclusivity of AI-related applications and products for women and older adults. The results of this research could have a direct application in the implementation of technology policies that affect social inclusion in Canadian society. It benefits both society and technological advances by guiding EDI-related initiatives into the science and technology discourse. The private sector will also benefit by re-thinking the recruitment and selection programs of the workforce.

It is vital to mention that our research is subject to some limitations, mainly regarding the Census data provided by Statistics Canada. This resource mentions that the survey does not include all types of current jobs in Canada, nor does it properly represent all communities. Therefore, our study is restricted to the inclusion of the identities listed in the Census questionnaire. This study analyzes the industries in which Canadian companies involved in AI-related research and development (R&D) operate. It is, therefore, important to note that patents and publications are just one key indicator for identifying R&D in the industrial setting.

Lastly, we would like to expand our research in progress to incorporate other baselines for comparison and other socio-economic attributes, such as unemployment and unemployment rate, union coverage, job permanency, employment by establishment size, working overtime, multiple job-holding and wage rate, in order to draw more insights towards the power of AI-related technological advancements on Canadian society.

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